

TO IMPROVE THE POSITION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE PRESS FREEDOM INDEX AND TO ORGANIZE EFFECTIVE MECHANISMS OF SYSTEMATIC COOPERATION WITH STATE BODIES AND ORGANIZATIONS

Mansur Yunusov

under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Head of the Department
of the Academy of Public Administration, associate professor
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7560350>

Abstract

This article describes the place of Uzbekistan in the index of freedom of speech in the world press freedom and the factors that serve to increase the quality of information openness policy in Uzbekistan today, the role and quality of leading personnel in ensuring information openness in public service.

Key words

press, freedom of speech, information, public service, mass media, information openness, public relations, censorship, world openness index, index, society, people, people,

Press Freedom Index or Press Freedom Index is an annual classification of countries compiled and published by the international non-governmental organization Reporters Without Borders based on indicators of press freedom in about 180 countries. A lower score indicates freedom of the press.

The Global Press Freedom Index is an annual survey published by the international non-governmental organization "Reporters Without Borders" and is an additional ranking of press freedom in countries around the world. The rating was published from 2001 to the present day. The last revision is scheduled for 2022.

The index divides countries according to the level of freedom of the press - from zero (the best indicator is the absence of any restrictions on the activities of the media) and above (the worst indicator). According to the organization's experts, the index can fully determine the state of freedom of speech in a single country. The country's place in the ranking depends on how free journalists and mass media in general are, what measures are taken by the country's authorities to create favorable conditions for the press. A detailed description of the rating methodology and related data sources are provided in the Reporters Without Borders annual report based on other comparative research results. There is also a similar ranking made by Freedom schhouse according to a different methodology.

"Press Freedom Index" of the Reporters Without Borders NGO conducts its work on the protection of press freedom, journalists and cyber citizens in the world (according to the results of 2021, the top three countries are Norway, Finland, Sweden; Uzbekistan is in 157th place; The last places are occupied by Eritrea, North Korea, Turkmenistan and China, respectively).

What is Uzbekistan doing to further improve its position in international rankings and indexes?

Reforms aimed at guaranteeing the protection of human rights, increasing the standard of living of the population, ensuring freedom in economic activity, and improving the material and

procedural norms in the judicial and legal sphere are the reason for the increase in the indicators of our country in international ratings and indexes. In particular, over the last four years, our country has risen to 52 places in the Heritage Fund's "Economic Freedom" index, 19 places in the World Bank's "Logistics Efficiency" index, and 18 places in the "Doing Business" index.

Also, with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6003 of June 2, "On improving the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international ratings and indices and introducing a new mechanism of systematic work with them in state bodies and organizations," the Republican Council for Working with International Ratings and Indices was established, the most important indicators of efficiency (KPI) according to the international rating and indices, which are a priority for the republic, have been approved.

World Press Freedom Index

Uzbekistan has moved up in the press freedom rating, but the situation remains "difficult". Uzbekistan ranked 133rd in the 2022 press freedom index of the Reporters Without Borders organization. A year ago, the country was 24 places lower. A strong change is due to the update of the rating methodology. The situation with press freedom in the country is still assessed as "difficult".

The international non-governmental organization "Reporters without Borders" (Reporters sans frontieres, RSF) announced the World Press Freedom Index 2022 on May 3, World Press Freedom Day. Uzbekistan took 20th place and 133rd place among 180 countries and regions. In last year's ranking, the country was 24 places lower - in 157th place. Working with a committee of seven experts from the worlds of science and media, RSF introduced five new indicators that capture the "complexity of press freedom": political context, legal framework, economic context, socio-cultural context and security (each with a score of 0

evaluated on a scale of up to 100 points). The study was conducted over the past year by interviewing hundreds of journalists, scientists and human rights activists using an updated questionnaire (123 questions). "Due to this change in methodology, caution should be exercised when comparing positions and scores between 2021 and 2022," the rating authors warn. The places in the rating have risen sharply in many countries, including neighboring countries of Uzbekistan. After the announcement of the rating, the press secretary of the President of Uzbekistan, Sherzod Asadov, congratulated the media representatives, saying, "This is one of the results of the important steps taken to ensure freedom under

the leadership of the head of our state.

The representative of the press service of the head of state, Komil Allamjonov, also noted that Uzbekistan's place in the ranking has improved. "So, if the press is less disturbed, we have a chance to

achieve a higher result. As our President said, there is no turning back! Only forward!" he wrote.

Ўзбекистоннинг матбуотдаги рейтинг яхшиландими?

Ўзбекистон оммавий ахборот воситалари эркинлиги билан боғлиқ вазият "қийин" деб баҳоланадиган давлатлар тоифасида қолди. Жами 42 та шундай давлат бор (2013 йилда улар сони 38 та эди). "Яхши" ҳолат атиги 8 та давлатда (26), "қониқарли" – 40 (27) давлатда, "муаммоли" – 62 (69) давлатда ва "жуда қийин" – 28 (20) та давлатда қайд этилган.

Рейтингда Ўзбекистоннинг энг яқин қўшнилари Уганда (132-ўрин) ва Жазоир (134-ўрин) бўлди. Қозоғистон 122-қаторда (ўтган йилга нисбатан +33 позиция), Тожикистон 152-ўринда (+10), Туркменистон 177-ўринда (+1) жойлашган. Қирғизистон 72-ўринни эгаллади (+7) ва яна Марказий Осиёда "беқарор иқтисодиёт ва кенг тарқалган расмий коррупцияга қарамай, нисбатан сўз ва матбуот эркинлигига эга" ягона давлатга айланд

Норвегия 92,65 балл билан рейтинг етакчиси бўлиб қолди. Ундан кейинги ўринларда Дания (90,27), учинчи ўринда Шветсия (88,84). Кучли ўнликка, шунингдек, Финляндия (88,42), Ирландия (88,3), Португалия (87,07), Литва (84,14) ва Лихтенштейн (84,03) киради.

Энг ёмон позициялар Шимолий Корея (180-ўрин, ўтган йилга нисбатан -1, 100 балдан 13,92 балл), Эритрея (179, +1, 19,62), Эрон (178, -4, 23,22), Туркменистон (177, +1), 25.01), Мянма (176, -36, 25.03), Хитой (175, +2, 25.17), Ветнам (174, +1, 26.11), Куба (173, -2, 27.32), Ироқ (172, -9), 28.59) ва Сурия (171, +2, 27.32).

"Devastating Consequences of Information Chaos"

RSF said the ranking results indicate "information chaos in 2022 - the devastating consequences of a globalized and digital space with a loose order that contributes to the spread of disinformation and propaganda."

"In democratic societies, the rise of Fox News-style opinion journalism and the widespread use of social media-enhanced disinformation channels are fueling ever-increasing public debate. Internationally, the asymmetry between open societies on the one hand and despotic regimes that control their media and information platforms by waging propaganda wars on the other weakens democratic regimes. At both levels, these two polarities are a factor in fueling tensions," the Reporters Without Borders report said.

The rankings are based in part on surveys using seven general criteria: pluralism (which measures the level of representation in the media space), media independence, environment and self-censorship, legal framework, transparency, infrastructure and abuse.

The survey took into account the legal framework of the media (including penalties for press offenses, the existence of state monopolies in certain types of media, and how media are regulated) and the degree of independence of state media. It also takes into account the assessment of violations of the free distribution of information on the Internet.

Violence against journalists, internet users and media workers, including violations committed by the state, armed police, secret organizations or pressure groups, is monitored by RSF staff throughout the year and taken into account as a final result. The organization said the low score in the report is consistent with increased press freedom. The questionnaire will be sent to Reporters Without Borders: 18 free speech NGOs on five continents, 150 reporters worldwide, as well as journalists, researchers, lawyers and human rights defenders.

According to the 2022 press freedom index, the five countries with the best conditions are Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Estonia and Finland. Norway is still the leader of the rating. Russia dropped five places to 155th place. Ukraine is in 106th place. As in 2021, Eritrea and North Korea close out the list, ranking 179th and 180th respectively. USA - 42nd, China - 175th place.

The methodology used in the compilation of the World Press Freedom Index, starting from 2022, the goal of the World Press Freedom Index is to compare the level of press freedom of journalists and mass media in 180 countries and territories. This comparison is based on the definition of press freedom formulated by RSF and its group of experts in the development of a new methodology that will be used from 2022:

"Freedom of the press is the ability of journalists, as individuals and communities, to choose, prepare and distribute news in the interests of society, independently of political, economic, legal and social interference, without threats to their physical and mental safety. "

The index is a snapshot of the situation in 180 countries and territories during the calendar year (January-December) before publication. Nevertheless, it is intended to accurately reflect the situation at the time of publication.

Therefore, when the press freedom situation in a country changes dramatically between the year-end assessment and publication, the data will be updated to take into account the most recent developments possible. This could be due to a new war, a coup d'état, an unprecedented or highly unusual large-scale attack on journalists, or the sudden introduction of highly repressive policies. For the 2022 index, this special procedure was used with Russia, Ukraine and Mali.

The ranking of regions and countries in this Index is based on a score from 0 to 100 for each country or region, with 100 being the best possible score (the highest possible level of press freedom) and 0 being the worst.

This score is calculated based on two components:

Quantitative calculation of abuses related to the activities of journalists and mass media;

a qualitative analysis of the situation in each country or territory based on the responses of press freedom experts (including journalists, researchers, academics and human rights defenders) to the RSF questionnaire, available in 23 languages.

The Press Freedom Map provides a visual representation of the scores of all countries in the index. Colors and classifications are defined as follows:

[85 - 100 points] good (green)

[70 - 85 points] [satisfactory (yellow)]

[55 - 70 points] [problematic (light orange)]

[40 - 55 points] [hard (dark orange)]

[0 - 40 points] [very serious (dark red)]

Evaluation criteria: five contextual indicators

Each country or territory's score is assessed using five contextual indicators that reflect the press freedom situation in all its complexity: political context, legal framework, economic context, socio-cultural context and security.

A utility score from 0 to 100 is calculated for each indicator. All auxiliary scores contribute equally to the global score. And within each indicator, all questions and sub-questions have equal weightage.

They are the degree of support and respect for the autonomy of the mass media in relation to political pressure by the state or other political entities;

the degree of acceptance of different journalistic approaches that meet professional standards, including politically aligned approaches and independent approaches;

the extent to which the media support politicians and the government in their role of holding them accountable for the public good.

They relate to the legislative and regulatory environment for journalists, in particular:

the degree of freedom of journalists and mass media to operate without censorship, judicial sanctions or excessive restrictions on their freedom of expression;

access to information without discrimination among journalists and the ability to protect sources;

impunity of persons guilty of acts of violence against journalists.

In particular, they aim to assess:

economic constraints related to government policies (including the difficulty of creating news media, favoritism and corruption in the allocation of public subsidies);

economic restrictions related to non-state participants (advertisers and commercial partners);

Economic restrictions on media owners seeking to promote or protect their business interests.

In particular, they aim to assess:

social restrictions resulting from press criticism and attacks based on issues such as gender, class, ethnicity and religion;

cultural constraints, including pressure on journalists not to question authority or influence at times, or not to cover certain issues because it conflicts with the dominant culture in the country or region.

Used literature:

1. www.pressindex.ru
2. www.aoka.uz
3. www.uza.uz
4. www.juornalist.uz
5. www.uchildiz.uz

